

UPDATING HERSTORY

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Cover: graphic reworking of a sheet from Van Dyck's Italian Sketchbook depicting Sofonisba Anguissola

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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Foreword

CARLA ROSSI

With this issue of *TCLA*, which is multilingual once again after the monographic edition published exclusively in Italian (dedicated to 16th-century Florentine artists), we have decided to pay tribute to a series of female artists of various nations and historical periods.

Women whose activity has been investigated too little or only superficially by historiographers. We have therefore proceeded, by means of new and precise archival research, mainly to update bio-bibliographical and art-historical data on a variety of themes: 15th-century copyists and illuminators active in the Monastero del Paradiso in Florence, Italy's first female architect Plautilla Bricci, Sofonisba Anguissola, Grisalda Bianchelli and Adriana Polissena, Asja Lācis, Sella Hasse and Elisabeth Voigt, Růžena Zátková, and – finally – Edmonia Lewis.

The issue ends with an interesting study, conducted by Maurizio Rebaudengo, in the archives of the Einaudi publishing house in Turin.

I would like to sincerely thank the authors of the research papers published here, whose efforts have made this new printing possible.

This special issue is published in Open Access in digital version only.

Asja Lācis: a Room of One's Own and Trajectories of Nonbelonging

JĀNIS TAURENS

Art Academy of Latvia

The realistic spirit encourages us to root around in the dusty rags of our lives. We are to look and see. Pay attention to particulars.

(Toril Moi. *Revolution of the Ordinary*)

I could begin with a rhetorical proposition that to compose a sentence and become famous is possible only in fiction, like Joseph Grand in the novel of Albert Camus *The Plague*. Or one can write a novel and receive a laurel wreath post-mortem like Sylvia Plath. But the best way to recognition for a woman is to become a mistress and/or a muse for a famous man, especially if her native language does not belong to any of the great Western literary traditions. It sounds ironical, but the life of Asja Lācis (1891–1979) which covers the period of World War I, the Russian Revolution, formation of the independent Latvian State (Republic of Latvia), Nazi Germany and the Great Terror of Stalin, as well as World War II and Soviet occupation of Latvia, is an excellent example of such a fate. Although she was a woman of deeds and not words, her writings in three languages – Latvian, Russian and German – consist of theoretical and autobiographical books and articles, partly in collaboration with others; the full bibliography of her works today is still not available.

Furthermore, Asja Lācis is mostly known neither as a theatre director, which was her key occupation during her lifetime, nor as a writer, but as an acquaintance of famous men – thinkers, stage directors, poets – such as Walter Benjamin, Bertolt Brecht and Erwin Piscator, to mention just a few. In the context of their achievements, a woman has merely the role of a muse or a witness of an epoch. This ‘Egypt of female servitude’ is not something new to feminist literary criticism, but in the case of Asja Lācis language also plays an important role in her ‘wandering in the wilderness’¹ (great part of her publications, as well as texts about her are in Latvian and Russian), geographical location in Eastern Europe, the ‘wrong’ political stance, as well as her work in such a ephemeral medium as

¹ See in Elaine Showalter’s article: E. Showalter, *Feminist Criticism in the Wilderness*, in E. Showalter (ed.), *The New Feminist Criticism: Essays on Women, Literature, and Theory*, Pantheon Books, New York, 1985, p. 243.

stage production. All these conditions have resulted in the marginalisation and cultural nonbelonging of Asja Lācis.

The motto of this article, which is the quotation from the Toril Moi's recent book on Ludwig Wittgenstein, John Langshaw Austin and Stanley Cavell,² suggests a methodological approach of this paper. It is not going to present some general theory; instead, I intend to argue for the originality and significance of some of Asja Lācis' theoretical and autobiographical writings. The article will be focused on the analysis of Lācis' role in writing the article on Naples, co-authored with Walter Benjamin, which up to now has not been fully recognised, especially concerning the genesis of the notion of porosity and how it is explained in the context of Benjamin's studies. Another possibly far-reaching but still ignored work of Lācis' is her monograph on the revolutionary German theatre. Analysing only one fragment from this book, I argue for its importance which along with Lācis' involvement in stage production can open up a new perspective on the origins of the performance and contemporary participatory art. It is necessary to note that Lācis' life and writings, as well as the reception and cultural recognition of her work are not clearly distinguishable. In other words, our understanding of her writings – articles and books – requires to take into account aspects of her life – both personal and professional – as well as to examine the history of her partial recognition.

By alluding to the well-known essay by Virginia Woolf in the title of the article, I would like to emphasise that, metaphorically speaking, Asja Lācis had no room of her own, neither in terms of language and native land, nor in terms of political and theoretical position. She published texts in three different languages, but her language skills were questioned. She worked as a stage director and actress in Latvia, Soviet Russia and Germany, but was forced to emigrate from Latvia because of her leftist political views. Furthermore, in the Soviet Union she was arrested and deported to the labour camp where she spent ten years. And, of course, it was not possible for Lācis to stay in Germany after the Nazis had seized power. Having returned from the camp, Lācis was not allowed to stay in Riga and she had to work in a small provincial town of Soviet Latvia. Although Lācis had a lifelong devotion to political theatre, her achievements in stage production have been hardly acknowledged after the restoration of the independence of the Republic of Latvia in 1991. Most of her

² T. Moi, *Revolution of the Ordinary: Literary Studies after Wittgenstein, Austin, and Cavell*, The University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London 2017, p. 63.

theoretical writings, except the book on German theatre, are mainly in Latvian, and nowadays they are even less discussed.³

Paradoxically, even her internationally known name 'Asja' is a nickname, coined when Anna Lācis (her maiden name was Anna Liepiņa) and her first husband Jūlijs Lācis were reading Ivan Turgenev's novella *Ася* (*Asya*) which portrays an unforgettable young girl. The nickname is appropriate for a muse of a man of letters, not an author and agent of history. In spoken and written English it is convenient to use the form of the family name 'Lācis' (in earlier German and English language publications without the length mark in 'a' as 'Lacis'), but in Latvian the nouns (also adjectives, pronouns and numerals) are declined in six cases and the endings of masculine and feminine grammatical genders differ. Nowadays we use a feminine form "Lāce" which can be declined (the masculine form of 'Lācis' if used as a family name for a woman cannot be declined). These linguistic nuances add yet one more perspective of non-belonging to the trajectories already outlined.

The article in the *Frankfurter Zeitung* on Naples

The German philosopher and author Martin Mittelmeier in his book on Theodor Adorno – *Adorno in Neapel: Wie sich eine Sehnsuchtslandschaft in Philosophie verwandelt* – discusses the concept of 'dialectical picture' on which the philosophy of Benjamin and Adorno is based, and mentions that Adorno's use of the term could come from the important conversation (*jenem denkwürdigen Gespräch* – as it is called in the correspondence between Adorno and Horkheimer) in 1929 at the Carlton Hotel in Frankfurt am Main where Adorno, Max Horkheimer, Benjamin, Lācis and Gretel Karplus participated.⁴ The fact of the conversation provides an impressive picture (the German

³ A recent publication of Andris Brinkmanis, a researcher from Latvia based in Italy, *Constellation Asja* is one of the few recognitions of Lācis' oeuvre on an international scale. See A. Brinkmanis, *Constellation Asja*, in *e-flux*, No. 110, June 2020.

Available online: <https://www.e-flux.com/journal/110/337321/constellation-asja/> (accessed 5 August 2021). See also the special issue of Canadian journal *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature* (March 2018, Vol. 45:1) with Susan Ingram as a guest editor, which gives account on different aspects of Lācis' life and professional work.

⁴ I use the Russian translation of the book politely sent to me by the author: М. Миттельмайер, *Адорно в Неаполе. Как страна мечты стала философией*, перевод – Виталий Серов, Ад Маргинем Пресс, Москва 2017, p. 118.

word *das Bild* would be more appropriate) of the vulnerability of women participants because the male philosophers have a *Gesammelte Schriften* in many volumes, but there are just a few publications discussing the role of Anna Lācis and Gretel Karplus. Rolf Wiggershaus in his fundamental work on the Frankfurt School, when describing this conversation, also mentions Asja Lācis and Gretel Karplus, but affording them the status of theatrical props: “The *Passagen-Werk* was also the point of contact for the discussions which Benjamin had with Adorno in Frankfurt and Königstein, at which Horkheimer, Gretel Karplus and Asja Lācis were also present from time to time.”⁵

Before that important conversation in August 19, 1925, an article *Neapel (Naples)* was published in the *Frankfurter Zeitung*. Asja Lācis and Walter Benjamin were named as authors of this essay. The short text has an important role in the development of Benjamin’s philosophical method best exemplified in his great oeuvre *Das Passagen-Werk* (in English translation *The Arcades Project*). The term ‘porosity’ from the article on Naples has been characterized as fresh and indispensable for the architectural theory, as well as a method of a new way of philosophical writing.⁶

Ernst Bloch even uses this term in the title of his essay *Italien und die Porosität (Italy and Porosity)*, acknowledging the inventors of the term – the authors of the article on Naples.⁷ But in the first postwar edition of Benjamin’s works, his friend and later editor Theodor Adorno denied any participation of Asja Lācis in writing of this article, stating that “*schwer ein Zweifel daran sein kann, daß diese Arbeit ganz und gar das Produkt Benjamins war*” (“there can be little doubt that this work was completely Benjamin’s product”). This quotation was from the endnotes for *Neapel* in Benjamin’s *Gesammelte Schriften*, the 4th volume edited by Tillman Rexroth, first published in 1972, where the authorship of Asja Lācis is acknowledged, but only as a fact of bibliographical information: “*Erst am 19.8.1925 wurde unter Asja Lācis’ und Walter Benjamin’s Namen Neapel in der Frankfurter Zeitung veröffentlicht.*” (“First publication of *Naples* was in 19.8.1925 in the *Frankfurter Zeitung* under the names of Asja Lācis and Walter Benjamin”).⁸

⁵ R. Wiggershaus, *The Frankfurt School: Its History, Theories, and Political Significance*, transl. by Michael Robertson, The MIT Press, Cambridge (MS) 1995, p. 89.

⁶ See the chapter on porosity in Martin Mittelmeier’s book on Adorno.

⁷ М. Миттельмайер, *Адорно в Неаполе*, p. 58.

⁸ W. Benjamin, *Gesammelte Schriften*, Bd. IV, hrsg. von Tillman Rexroth, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1991, p. 987.

The most recent and complete biography of Benjamin available today in English by Howard Eiland and Michael W. Jennings, published in 2014, is very short on this point. After a long quotation from the article on Naples about porosity Eiland and Jennings conclude: “Just as there is no doubt that the essay is in some sense co-authored, there is little doubt that the German prose is entirely Benjamin’s.”⁹

In the endnotes commenting this sentence, they are more indecisive: “Adorno asserted that the text was Benjamin’s alone – ‘There can be little doubt that this work was completely Benjamin’s product’ [as you see, this statement by Adorno is extensively quoted] – a judgment in keeping with a general tendency on the part of Benjamin’s friends and readers to denigrate Lacis and her role in his life. A corrective to this position is supplied by Ingram, *The Writing of Asja Lacis*”.¹⁰ The first statement by Eiland and Jennings needs a closer examination. The authorship of Lacis is acknowledged with remark ‘in some sense’ and if you want you will read it in such a way, that Benjamin being in love with Lacis included his new acquaintance as an author. The second part of the sentence speaks about the linguistic form – ‘the German prose’ – which having in the background the powerful image of the development of art and literature as a progress of formal innovations¹¹ implies that this article in some important sense is Benjamin’s. In the four volume edition of Benjamin’s works in English – *Selected Writings* – we can find out that *Naples* is written by Benjamin together with Asja Lacis,¹² and the *Chronology* given at the end of the first volume expands a little bit on their relationship by quoting famous passage

⁹ H. Eiland and M. W. Jennings, *Walter Benjamin: A Critical Life*, The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge (MS), London 2014, p. 211.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 697 n24.

¹¹ See, for example, excellent characterisation of formal innovations in visual art which for a long time was unquestionably accepted: “According to that polarity [form versus content, style versus expression], emergent feminist work was often placed simplistically on the side of content and expression; seeming to exhibit no proper formal concerns, it could be easily exiled altogether from ‘art’ proper and certainly from understanding a history modernism in its own terms.” (G. Pollock, *After-affects | After-images: Trauma and aesthetic transformation in the virtual feminist museum*, Manchester University Press, Manchester 2013, p. 98.)

¹² W. Benjamin, *Selected Writings*. Vol. 1. Ed. by Marcus Bullock and Michael W. Jennings. The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge (MS), London 1996, p. 414.

from Benjamin's letter to Gershom Scholem about "a Bolshevik Latvian woman from Riga" whom Benjamin met in Capri.¹³

The editor's commentary acknowledges the importance of the indirect references to Lācis in Benjamin's letters to Scholem: "Though he [namely – Benjamin] describes his visits to the Italian mainland, he does not mention that he travelled with her [namely – Lācis] as her companion, nor does he state explicitly that she was his collaborator on the vivid account of his impressions entitled *Naples* – the first of many such city images – even though he mentions that it 'will be published in Latvian and perhaps in German' (Letters, 253) [the reference here is to the English translation of the correspondence of Benjamin]."¹⁴ The proposition about the possibilities of a publication seems shocking: Benjamin has a fair copy (*ich die Reinschrift habe*), which is going to be published in Latvian (*sic!*) and maybe (*vielleicht*) in German. Unfortunately, the article never appeared in Latvian and there is no information about the Latvian version of *Naples*. Margarita Miglāne, a theatre researcher from Latvia, in her article about Lācis quoted her letter to Andrejs Upīts, the writer and the Head of Literary Unit of Latvian monthly magazine *Domas (Thoughts)*: "I am hurrying up to send you *Jauno vācu režiju [The new German stage production]. Neapole [Naples]* also is finished. But in German. Because I must write tour descriptions for one German publishing house. I would like to publish at first in your magazine."¹⁵ The letter provides evidence that Lācis at the time had a more definite creative plan than Benjamin of writing for Latvian as well as German magazines. For unknown reasons, the implementation of her intentions was hindered.

This information was not available for the authors composing Benjamin's biography, allowing them only to mention contradictory opinions and leaving the final decision to the

¹³ M. Bullock and M. W. Jennings, *Chronology*, in W. Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, Vol. 1, p. 510. See original phrase and its context in Benjamin's letter from Capri (June 13, 1924): "*Eine bolschewistische Lettin aus Riga, die am Theater spielt und Regie führt ...*" (W. Benjamin, *Briefe*, Bd. I, hrsg. von Gershom Scholem und Theodor W. Adorno, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1978, p. 347). In the commentary the word 'Lettin' is deciphered as 'Asja Lacis' (*ibid.*, p. 350).

¹⁴ M. Bullock and M. W. Jennings, *Chronology*, p. 510. It is the letter composed in Rome and Florence, October 12–November 5, 1924: "*Dann wird sowie ich die Reinschrift habe, lettisch, und vielleicht auch deutsch "Neapel" erscheinen.*" (W. Benjamin, *Briefe*, Bd. I, p. 362). Commenting on this sentence, the authors mention only the date of publication in *Frankfurter Zeitung (Chronology)*, p. 365).

¹⁵ M. Miglāne, *Tu ienāci pulkā*, in M. Miglāne et al. *Anna Lācis*, Liesma, Riga 1973, p. 34. The quotation is without date; monthly magazine *Domas* was published from 1912 to 1915 and from 1924 to 1934, and a possible date of the letter could be in 1924 or in 1925.

readers – to agree with Theodor Adorno or Susan Ingram. Nevertheless, besides the aforementioned Ingram’s article, there are also other publications, which acknowledge Lācis’ involvement in writing of *Naples*. For instance, Hildegard Brenner in her *Nachwort* for German autobiography of Lācis, which includes also about one third of *Naples*, argues that those passages of the article are chosen which are self-contained and “let acknowledge the co-authorship of Asja Lācis”.¹⁶ Still, this statement sounds quite cautious and that is understandable because the book – as can be seen from the title – is addressed to the devotees of Benjamin, Brecht, Piscator and Vsevolod Meyerhold.

The writing of article about Naples is also inquired in the book by a Latvian researcher Beata Paškevica providing an analysis of Lācis’ activities in the theatre and her relationships with Benjamin and Brecht.¹⁷ Paškevica mentions the infamous opinion by Adorno that “there can be little doubt etc.”,¹⁸ but she also quotes three letters which Lācis had addressed to a Latvian actress Elvīra Bramberga.¹⁹ This material provides evidence of Lācis’ perception of this Italian city, its ‘oriental’ appearance and the fascinating vivacity of the street life:

I was very fond of Naples – a mad city: perpetual movement, sharp piercing noises from vendors, donkeys and kids. Street musicians playing and singing on streets at night – absolutely orientally – surrounded by hundreds of children with black mouths, fingers in the mouth – but their black eyes sparkling with joy of the heard sounds. All the life happens outside – narrow streets, doors opened (...).²⁰ I am till now in Capri. At the moment I am writing to you on the balcony – Vesuvius with plumes of smoke is in front of me and the silhouette of Naples can be seen over the

¹⁶ H. Brenner, *Nachwort* in A. Lācis, *Revolutionär im Beruf: Berichte über Meyerhold, Brecht, Benjamin und Piscator*, hrsg. von Hildegard Brenner, Rogner & Bernhard, München 1971, p. 124.

¹⁷ B. Paškevica, *In der Stadt der Parolen: Asja Lācis, Walter Benjamin und Bertolt Brecht*, Klartext Verlag, Essen 2006, pp. 173–180.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 173.

¹⁹ Now the letters are in the Museum of Literature and Music in Riga.

²⁰ May 8, 1924. B. Paškevica, *In der Stadt der Parolen*, p. 174 n49. In the footnotes Paškevica gives the text of the letters in Latvian. We can see that at that time the writing of ‘Naples’ was different from today’s Latvian (‘*Neapole*’): Lācis used the spelling closer to German – ‘*Neapele*’.

sea. (...) The street is wonderful – a street is more powerful than a house. It is also more significant and necessary for people.²¹

Paškevica argues that the letters acknowledge the involvement of Lācis in writing of the article, especially due to her sensibility to the poverty of the children. The topic was familiar to Lācis since she had already worked with orphans and children of the street when organizing the children's theatre in Oryol, Soviet Russia, in 1918–1919.²²

Another remarkable likeness between the letters and the article is the vivid descriptions of the street life. It could, of course, have impressed both northerners, the difference being that Benjamin has later texts about other cities as well, for example on Marseilles or Moscow, where he similarly has described the astonishing sights of the street life. Nevertheless, some features of *Naples* undoubtedly come from Asja Lācis, especially those which pertain to the performative aspects of the outdoor city life which she can compare with her theatre experience:

Buildings are used as a popular stage. They are all divided into innumerable, simultaneously animated theatres. Balcony, courtyard, window, gateway, staircase, roof are at the same time stage and boxes. Even the most wretched pauper is sovereign in the dim, dual awareness of the participating, in all its destitution, in one of the pictures of Neapolitan street life that will never return, and of enjoying in all his poverty the leisure to follow the great panorama. What is enacted on the staircases is an advanced school of stage management.²³

“An advanced school of stage management” (“*Eine hohe Schule der Regie*” in German) is, of course, a phrase of Lācis who herself worked as a stage director. Martin Mittelmeier in his book on Adorno even provides a photograph of one of Vsevolod Meyerhold's spectacles

²¹ June 30, 1924. Ibid., p. 175 n51. As regards the sentence ‘writing to you on the balcony’, Paškevica proposes that it could be the balcony of Benjamin's house (ibid., p. 175n50).

²² Ibid., p. 176.

²³ W. Benjamin and A. Lācis, *Naples*, in W. Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, Vol. 1, 1913–1926, ed. by Marcus Bullock and Michael W. Jennings, The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge (MS), London 1996, p. 417. German original: W. Benjamin und A. Lācis, *Neapel*, in W. Benjamin, *Gesammelte Schriften*, Bd. IV, hrsg. von Tillman Rexroth. Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1991, p. 310. See also: A. Lācis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 47.

in 1922 in Moscow – *The Magnanimous Cuckold* – where the stage design resembles the above quoted description of Naples.²⁴ Lācis had seen Meyerhold’s theatrical spectacles even before and also after the October Revolution, and in her memories she acknowledges his influence. In the book *Revolutionär im Beruf* she states very clearly that in her work as a stage director and a theatre critic in Oryol, Riga, Moscow, Kazakhstan and Valmiera (the provincial Latvian town Lācis was confined to after her deportation to Kazakhstan) she was in great debt to Meyerhold.²⁵

The question of authorship becomes even more important concerning the notion of porosity. The quoted fragment about ‘the advanced school of stage management’ is intended as a paradigmatic example of porosity. It begins with an assertion: “Porosity results not only from the indolence of the southern artisan, but also, above all, from the passion for improvisation, which demands that space and opportunity be preserved at any price.”²⁶ Porosity here does not mean static spatial or geological qualities of Naples but instead it refers to the dynamic performative forms of everyday life, which are close to the professional activities of Lācis. Also in her memoirs in German Lācis wrote: “One day I said that buildings looked porous.” And then she retold Benjamin’s proposal to write together the article on Naples ending with a short resume: “And we wrote it.”²⁷ In the letter to Elvīra Bramberga she supplies additional details of her authorship: “And I also had a proposal from one publishing house to visit Spain and to write a tour description, because I had written the *Naples* which they appreciated very much, together with one philosopher.”²⁸

It is possible that the notion of porosity indirectly emerged due to Bertolt Brecht’s arrival in Capri. His descriptions of the nearby Positano were so fascinating that Lācis agreed to visit the stage designer Caspar Neher. They travelled with a motor boat and Positano from the sea “looked like the bee-hive, people lived in the cells carved in rocks”.²⁹ Martin

²⁴ М. Миттельмайер, *Адорно в Неаполе*, p. 55.

²⁵ A. Lacis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 21. See also: А. Лацис, *Красная звезда*, Издание книжного магазина “Циолковский”, Москва 2018, pp. 46–47.

²⁶ W. Benjamin and A. Lacis, *Naples*, pp. 416–417.

²⁷ A. Lacis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 46.

²⁸ March 20, 1925. Quoted after B. Paškevica, *In der Stadt der Parolen*, p. 179n65.

²⁹ A. Lacis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 41. At that time Benjamin was not introduced to Brecht by Lācis, the friendship of both men began later.

Mittelmeier³⁰ proposes still another source of the notion, which could be known to Lācis and Bernhard Reich, her lifelong friend and later second husband: porosity is mentioned in the first chapter of Thomas Mann's novel *Der Zauberberg* (*The Magic Mountain*). This chapter was published in May 1920 in the newspaper *Neue Züricher Zeitung* before printing the finished novel in 1924. Benjamin, as we can conclude from his letter to Gershom Scholem (April 6, 1925), had read the book after the article on Naples was finished, but Lācis and Reich could have been impressed by the description of “a long building, with a cupola and so many balconies that from a distance it looked porous, like a sponge”.³¹ Those considerations, although hypothetical, are important because they involve Asja Lācis and her other acquaintances in the genealogy of the notion which traditionally is associated with Benjamin and his philosophical method.

We can also compare some other publications of Asja Lācis with the article on Naples.³² In 1922, she published a short review about German theatre in the left wing newspaper *Darbs un maize* (the Latvian title of the newspaper translates as *Work and Bread*). In 1924 and 1925 three publications in *Domas* (*Thoughts: Monthly Review of Literature, Science and Art*) followed which was one of the most important left wing cultural magazine in Latvia at the time. The article *Parīzes ikdiena un teātris* (*Everyday Life and Theatre in Paris*) was published in the September issue of *Domas* in 1925, approximately at the same time as *Neapel* in *Frankfurter Zeitung*. Before discussing particular stage productions, Lācis shares her impressions of Paris. Sentences are – unlike Benjamin's – very short, sometimes expressed in only one word. I will give some examples from the first two paragraphs:

Railway station *Paris Garre de Lion*. A long row of cars near the station. I am rushing forth in an admirable speed. I am already near Sorbonne, I am pulling up

³⁰ М. Миттельмайер, *Адорно в Неаполе*, p. 51 n122.

³¹ T. Mann, *The Magic Mountain*, transl. by H. T. Lowe-Porter, Vintage Books, London 1999, p. 9.

³² See two incomplete bibliographies of Lācis' works: M. Miglāne et al., *Anna Lācis*, pp. 250–255 and B. Paškevica, *In der Stadt der Parolen*, pp. 317–322. In both bibliographies the titles of articles are in now adopted Latvian spelling. Original titles are: *Berlines teatru eespaidi* (in the section *Māksla un kultūra*, newspaper *Darbs un Maize*, No 6, 1922), *Vācijas teatrs* (in two parts, monthly magazine *Domas*, No, 6 and 7, 1924, pp. 49–52, 155–159), *Berlines teatru pagahjuschà sesona* (*Sozialdemokrats*, November 15, signed as 'Anna Lahzis'), *Jaunā vācu režija* (*Domas*, No. 3, 1925, pp. 194–198), *Parizes ikdeéna un teatris* (*Domas*, No. 9, 1925, pp. 285–291). With these titles the articles are available online at the National Digital Library of Latvia (*Latvijas Nacionālā digitālā bibliotēka*): <http://www.periodika.lv/> (accessed 5 August 2021).

at *Hôtel de Flandre*. Quickly, easy and cheap – only 14 francs. In Berlin the same [trip] would cost 20 francs. The hostess with a dark hair and fat, a tasteless waiting room – an imitation of Rococo, all around many coverlets in the style of Richelieu, doll-like windows, curtains trimmed with lace – at all places oleanders.³³

The same writing style can be noticed a bit later: “Morning. Misty. Breakfast in café. Round shining metallic bar.” Again about prices, about sculptures in the gardens as imitations of the Greek ones, some remarks about architecture. Prices were important to Lācis because she was a representative of ‘the intellectual proletariat’ from Eastern Europe.³⁴ The main theme of Lācis’ article is theatre production, but she compares also the number of the sold book copies in France and Germany (as an example using Thomas Mann’s *Der Zauberberg*). In addition, she discusses advertisements, Parisian women, their objectification (not using exactly this term), but also the possibility to adopt the form of the French revue for the proletariat theatre in Berlin.³⁵

Another succinct statement treats ‘the entertainment industry’ (*‘izpriecas industrija’* – in Latvian): “Grandguignole³⁶, Revue and vaudevilles serve for the entertainment industry. Especially for the English and American visitors and the folks from province.”³⁷ This must remind us about the chapter *The Culture Industry: Enlightenment as Mass Deception* in Adorno and Horkheimer’s book *Dialectic of Enlightenment* written about twenty years later. One more feature that first appeared in this article and was later developed in Lācis’ book on German theatre is the relations of the stage production and cinema (which is, of course, an important theme in Benjamin’s most famous essay – *The Work of Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction*). Here, at the end of the article, she describes her impression

³³ A. Lācis, *Parizes ikdeēna un teatris*, in *Domas*, No. 9, 1925, p. 285.

³⁴ Although the phrase ‘itinerant intellectual proletariat’ (*ein intellektuelles Wanderproletariat*) is Benjamin’s (used in review about Jakob Job’s tour description of Naples – see W. Benjamin, *Kritiken und Rezensionen: Jakob Job, Neapel. Reisebilder und Skizzen*, in *Gesammelte Schriften*, Bd. III, hrsg. von Hella Tiedemann-Bartels, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1991 [1972], p. 133) and he himself was aware of the financial pressure, nevertheless Asja Lācis and Walter Benjamin were the representatives of different classes – the proletariat and bourgeoisie – and the term is more appropriate in the case of Lācis.

³⁵ A. Lācis, *Parizes ikdeēna un teatris*, p. 286.

³⁶ *Le Théâtre du Grand-Guignol* (The Theatre of the Great Puppet) – was a theatre in Paris known for its horror shows.

³⁷ A. Lācis, *Parizes ikdeēna un teatris*, p. 287.

of 'Picabia's film' which like Pagliacci jumps out of the corner and contrary to traditional film transforms the tragic into comic.³⁸ Her brief but sharp and precise phrases are not like Benjamin's, who would expand them in a complicated syntactic structure. Lācis' style is determined by her gender and class, as well as cultural and historical background. It is evident that the Marxist views expressed by Lācis here are congenial to the ideas later shared by the representatives of the Frankfurt School, only her aphoristic statements have a chronological priority, but her belonging to the School is not seriously considered. The text on Paris – though here analysed only partially – reveals her expressive style as an independent stage director and a politically active woman. Had the Latvian version of *Naples* been published, we, perhaps, could be able to say with greater conviction: this is a groundbreaking work, written, without doubt, by Asja Lācis and in her style, while the male name had been added just for publishing reasons.

Autobiographical writings

Part of Asja Lācis' written works consists of autobiographical writings in German (together with Hildegard Brenner, 1971, second edition 1976), in Latvian (in book *Anna Lācis*, preceded with three essays on her life and work as a stage director, 1973), and in Russian (published in 1984, with remark 'written down by Jurij Karagach', second edition 2018 without mentioning Karagach). There are also at least six publications in Latvian periodicals in the 1966–1971 period titled as *No piezīmju burnīcas (From the Notebooks)*. Most of the memories are written more than 40 years after the events described.³⁹

If I had to draw a conclusion in one sentence, I would say that it is impossible to create one coherent autobiography out of these publications. There are several reasons why it is so, and I will try to describe some of them.

First of all, the book in German edited by Hildegard Brenner *Revolutionär im Beruf* has a subtitle *Berichte über proletarisches Theater, über Meyerhold, Brecht, Benjamin und Piscator* and, as Susan Ingram writes, it "is indicative of Brenner's interest. Lācis

³⁸ Ibid. p. 291; actually it is *Entr'acte* by René Clair, premiered in Francis Picabia's *Relâche*. The film is a milestone event in the history of Surrealism and in the development of performance art (see in R. Goldberg, *Performance Art: From Futurism to the Present*, revised and enlarged edition, Thames and Hudson, London 1999, pp. 90–95).

³⁹ See the bibliography in the book by M. Miglāne et al., *Anna Lācis*, pp. 250–255, and in B. Paškevica, *In der Stadt der Parolen*, pp. 317–322.

concentrates on what she was able to add to knowledge about well-known, left-leaning, male personalities.”⁴⁰

Ingram argues that her Russian memoirs, *Красная гвоздика* (*The Red Carnation*), is “Lācis’s story as she chose to rewrite, and expand upon, the German version and it diverges from Brenner’s assemblage in key respects resulting in a much more personable perception of her”.⁴¹ But in the *Afterword* to the second edition of *The Red Carnation* (which included a Russian translation of the *Naples*) Anna Nizhnik (*Анна Нижник*) comments that these memoirs are not written by Lācis and are based on the German version and additional interviews given by Lācis to Alexandra Malceva (*Александра Мальцева*) on Bernhard Reich. Nizhnik refers to the unpublished Lācis’ letters to her Russian friend and theatre theorist Alexander Fevralskij (*Александр Февральский*). In one of them Lācis complains that her autobiography is given to the Latvian publishing house *Liesma* in the version edited by Kljuev (*Клюев* – first name not given) and only signed as “written down by Jurij Karagach” (*Юрий Карагач*), and that “all that is important to me is excluded from the manuscript”.⁴² Ironically enough, Jurij Karagach was at that time a popular author writing about Soviet commissars.⁴³

Nevertheless, the book comprises a more diverse biographical data compared to *Revolutionär im Beruf* or Lācis’ autobiographical publications in Latvian. For example, the difference is visible in the description of the first meeting with Benjamin in Capri. In Russian memoirs we find an arresting detail – after the account of their first meeting in a shop where Lācis went to buy almonds but forgot the Italian name for them, and Benjamin helped her, the Russian text proceeds:⁴⁴ “I said my name, and he offered to bring the packages to my home but at once they fell out of his hands. We both burst out laughing”.⁴⁵

Only in this Russian version of her memoirs do we find the detail of their laughing which could be the beginning of their romantic relations. It is rather unlikely that this detail would be given in the interview about Reich or that it was invented by editor.

⁴⁰ Susan Ingram, *The Writing of Asja Lācis*, in *The New German Critique*, No. 86, 2002, pp. 162–163.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, p. 170.

⁴² А. Нижник, *Послесловие*, in А. Лацис, *Красная гвоздика*, Издание книжного магазина “Циолковский”, Москва 2018, pp. 219–220.

⁴³ *Ibid.*, p. 220.

⁴⁴ More detailed analysis see in: J. Taurens, *Asja Lācis and Walter Benjamin: Translating Different Cities*, in *Canadian Review of Comparative Literature*, March 2018, Vol. 45:1 pp. 18–19.

⁴⁵ А. Лацис, *Красная гвоздика*, p. 90.

The autobiographical publications in Latvian periodicals are on most occasions more expanded than the book *Anna Lācis* published in Latvian in 1973. Comparing all the autobiographical texts, it can be suggested that Lācis had chosen several moments of her life and had retold them with changing details, not only adjusting to a possible reader, but also responding to the interests of the editor (as in the case of Hildegard Brenner) and omitting some events (or they have been erased by the editor as in the case of her Russian memoirs).

There is another important source of her biography, which must be mentioned – the life story of Asja Lācis told by her daughter Dagmāra Ķimele. The book was co-written by Dagmāra Ķimele and journalist Gunta Strautmane and published with the title *Asja. Režisores Annas Lācis dēkainā dzīve (Asja: The Adventurous Life of the Stage Director Anna Lāce)*. Though it is beyond the scope of this article to analyse it here in details, the memories of her daughter – written with embitterment and even hatred – are important in yet another aspect. They attest to the failure of Asja Lācis to fulfil the role of a mother as it was expected from her. There is a personal truth in Dagmāra Ķimele's embitterment, but we can see it also as a consequence of patriarchal prejudices. Walter Benjamin also was not a good father to his son Stefan, but this plays no role in Benjaminology – he is a great philosopher and the family life is secondary to his intellectual achievements.

Not only it is impossible to create one textually coherent autobiography of Anna Lācis, but also over her lifetime there are several things, which have been passed over in silence. She was reluctant to speak about the ten years in the labour camp in Kazakhstan, the longest description of this period of her life is in her German memoirs: “*Ich wurde gezwungen, zehn Jahre in Kasachstan zu verbringen*” (“I was forced to spend ten years in Kazakhstan”).⁴⁶ Also other documentary sources (interviews, memories, etc.) can be used but their examination reveals that an attitude to such a complicated and artistically vivid female personality as Asja Lācis has never been neutral. For example, Valentīna Freimane (1922–2018), a prominent Latvian film and theatre historian, in the interview to Anna Alchuk (*Анна Альчук*) draws a controversial portrait of Lācis, generalising that: “All the great people, especially great women, are interesting because they have many alogical, absurd inner impulses, which in concordance with the normal logic must be conflicting, but they

⁴⁶ A. Lācis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 77.

are not”.⁴⁷ Freimane even casts doubts on Lācis’ language skills, unexpectedly also on her Latvian: “She [Asja Lācis] spoke equally poorly in all languages, except Latvian, though her written Latvian also had mistakes”.⁴⁸ Nevertheless, we must take into account that Freimane met Lācis in the 1960s and 1970s when she lived in Soviet Latvia without having a possibility to practice her German and – living in province – did not need Russian in her everyday communication. Furthermore, it has to be noted that Freimane, as she herself acknowledged at the beginning of the interview, was a friend of Dagmāra Ķimele, the daughter of Asja Lācis, and thus, we can assume, had accepted Dagmāra Ķimele’s hostility to her mother. Therefore, Lācis did not succeed in building a coherent self-image even in the autobiographical creation of the room of one’s own.

Texts on theatre

The most important Asja Lācis’ theoretical text is a monograph in Russian on the revolutionary theatre in Germany. It was published by the well-known Soviet publishing house *Художественная Литература* (meaning ‘literary fiction’). Both the already mentioned bibliographies of Lācis’ writings simply state that her book is written in Russian and published in Moscow, in 1935. The red front cover of the book features her name in Russian letters (*Анна Лацис*), title (*Революционный театр Германии*) and shortening of the publishing house with the year (*Гослитиздат 1935*), but on the first page under the title there is a remark ‘перевел с немецкой рукописи И. Бархаш’ (translated from the German manuscript by I. Barhash; Russian word ‘*рукопись*’, literary meaning ‘handwriting’, can also refer to a printed manuscript). This fact is omitted in both bibliographies and there is no further information about the possible manuscript in German and its fate. It could have disappeared after her arrest and subsequent deportation in 1938 as did the letters from Walter Benjamin.

The fragment of this book is included in Lācis’ memoirs edited by Hildegard Brenner (*Revolutionär in Beruf*), but it is translated from Russian by N. K. Zatirow. In these

⁴⁷ А. Альчук, “Это бы очень украсило мою биографию”... Любовь и революция в судьбе Аси Лацис, Вальтера Беньямина и Бернхарда Райха in *Гендерные исследования*, No. 17, 2008, p. 173. For the reference to this interview I owe Susan Ingram’s article on Lācis: S. Ingram, *Lācis as a Multilingual Ecosophy*, in *Tusaaji: A Translation Review*, Vol. 5, No. 5, 2016, pp. 63–81.

⁴⁸ А. Альчук, “Это бы очень украсило мою биографию”, p. 174.

memoirs Lācis or Brenner quotes one letter of Benjamin where he writes that he will send her his recent work and asks the same from her: “*Dagegen bitte ich Dich natürlich um dein Buch.*” (“For it I ask, of course, your book”).⁴⁹

At the end of the publication of this *Briefentwurf* (the draft of a letter) of 1935 there is an editor’s remark that the mentioned book is her *Revolutionäres Theater in Deutschland*, published in Russian in 1935, in Moscow.⁵⁰ This brief information without further comments sounds puzzling because Benjamin did not know Russian, but it strengthens the assumption about the existence of the German manuscript.

If Valentīna Freimane’s account of Lācis’ language skills was correct, the book on German theatre might have been written with the help of Bernhard Reich, the second husband of Lācis and her lifelong friend. Besides, the book also relies on many German sources. Nevertheless, if we compare it with the memories written by Reich and published in Russian at the end of his life in 1972, which ponders upon his theatrical experience in Vienna, Berlin and Moscow, we see that the description of the same theatre events are different. If Lācis tried to relate every detail of the theatre life to economic, social and political background in a clearly Marxist manner, Reich was more concerned with personalities and their characterisation.⁵¹

Not only Asja Lācis writes about professional theatre, but she also analyses the amateur performances of the working class theatrical collectives, their organisation and political struggle, even after the Nazi Party came to power. The book covers the period before the German revolution of 1918 until the events in 1934. It also features chapters on the German expressionist theatre familiar to Lācis from her personal experience. This is an indispensable source in the history of German theatre; nevertheless, it is not well-known due to its language.

The significance of this book can also be affirmed from the perspective of the genealogy of contemporary art. Claire Bishop in her work on participatory art – *Artificial Hells: Participatory Art and the Politics of Spectatorship* – published in 2012, writes about the Brazilian director Augusto Boal and his ‘invisible theater’ in the 1960s as an important forerunner of the participatory art: “Of the many innovations in social theater that Boal devised, the most relevant to contemporary art is Invisible Theater, developed in Buenos

⁴⁹ A. Lācis, *Revolutionär im Beruf*, p. 72.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 73.

⁵¹ See Б. Райх, *Вена— Берлин— Москва— Берлин*, Искусство, Москва 1972.

Aires as an unframed mode of public and participatory action designed to avoid detection by police authorities”.⁵² Bishop describes one of the ‘plays’ which is a ‘constructed situation in a restaurant’,⁵³ but the same principle – only as a constructed situation on the platform of Berlin’s metro – was already described in Lācis’ book and pertains to theatrical experiments thirty year earlier. In the situation of a constantly increasing censorship in the Nazi Germany, the workers political theatre had to change its form of performance and use everyday situations for improvised theatrical sketches:

Cram-full platform of metro in Berlin. Suddenly in the turmoil of passengers one man falls down – fainted. People swarm around the miserable, and a discussion flashes up. One of the passengers exclaims: “Unemployed!” Another tells a story of the unfortunate man. The third interferes revealing the injustice of a bourgeois state. Somebody sets forth the political programme of the Third Reich, the National Socialist programme. His neighbour intrudes, gives hell to the national socialist, and states the principles of the Communist Party. When the passengers finally get on the train, on the road they revise the situation and the discussion. Neither of them nor the policeman standing nearby suspect that the fainting and the discussion were staged, and that they participated in a performance piece of a banned agitprop troupe which was working under the conditions of the bourgeois terror.⁵⁴

In both occasions – in Buenos Aires in the 1960s and in Berlin in the 1930s – the spectators did not know that they were participating in a spectacle, and of course such spectacles can easily avoid the censorship of police. Tracing back the history of contemporary art to such

⁵² C. Bishop, *Artificial Hells: Participatory Art and the Politics of Spectatorship*, Verso, London and New York 2012, p.122.

⁵³ *Ibid.*, p. 123.

⁵⁴ А. Лацис, *Революционный театр Германии*, перевел с немецкой рукописи И. Бархаш, Художественная Литература, Москва 1935, p. 228. Lācis does not give the year of such invisible performances, but the quoted fragment is from the 17th chapter where she states that at the end of 1930 the agitprop troupes were banned (*ibid.*, p. 223).

experiments, the performance in Berlin described by Asja Lācis acquires a status of an ignored but paradigmatic example.⁵⁵

There is another important question: why Asja Lācis paid so much attention to amateur theatre of the working class? One possible answer can be found in her experience in the 1920s when Lācis collaborated with ‘the pursued theatre’ in Latvia, namely, the proletarian political theatre, as a stage director.⁵⁶ Although the performances of ‘the pursued theatre’ were not invisible in the same sense as those in Berlin and Buenos Aires, they exhibit similar features. The short plays written by Latvian poet Leons Paegle and staged by Asja Lācis – called ‘charades’ – could be mentioned as one of the examples. In these charades, the spectators had to guess the parts of a political slogan or a word, which helped them to come to a political conclusion. Performances were intended for the narrow rooms of a workers club without decorations, and personages were characterised by a telling detail. The political message of such charades was communicated in a brief time interval, which was an important aspect because the performances were sometimes interrupted by police.⁵⁷

In her memoirs in Russian, Lācis has retold the performance of Paegle’s *Charade No 1* emphasising this aspect of censorship. She also remembered how the performances were assisted by children – she had organised them in ‘the underground pioneer group’ – who unmistakably recognised the disguised agents of police.⁵⁸ In her memoirs Lācis also states that ‘the pursued theatre’ belongs to the tradition of ‘the international political theatre’⁵⁹ and thus – we can conclude – it must be incorporated in a broader history of theatre and politically oriented art. Unfortunately, accounts of the working class amateur theatre are rarely included in the history of professional theatre.

⁵⁵ For more on this aspect of Lācis’ work see: J. Taurens, *No objekta uz notikumu un darbību: politiskā teātra piemērs* [From object to event and action: the example of a political theatre], in *Acta Academiae Artium*, ed. by Agnija Lesničēnoka. Art Academy of Latvia, Riga: 2020, pp. 224–233.

⁵⁶ The first article on the ‘pursued theatre’ was also written by Lācis – see A. Lācis, *Vajātais teātris*, in *Dramaturģija un teātris*, Latvijas Valsts izdevniecība, Riga 1962, pp. 9–40. See also S. Freinberga, “*Vajātā teātra*” laiks, in M. Miglāne, et al. *Anna Lācis*, pp. 75–114. The term was created by Latvian poet Linards Laicens (1883–1938) who devoted to Asja Lācis love poems *Ho-Taī*.

⁵⁷ On charades see L. Paegle, *Kas ir skatuves šarade, un kā to uzvest* [What is a charade and how to stage it], in *Vienība*, No. 17, 1924.

⁵⁸ А. Лацис, *Красная звезда*, pp. 113–114.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 106.

Scattered across various languages and political regimes, Asja Lācis embodies an ambiguous figure of cultural and intellectual nonbelonging. Her authorship of the article on Naples till now has been denied or denigrated, although Lācis' contribution to the formation of the notion of porosity, as well as her possible impact on the methodological development of the Frankfurt School is very credible. Lācis' monograph on the revolutionary German theatre has been ignored despite its authentic materials, which, among other, suggest a new perspective on the genealogy of the contemporary art practices, especially the genre of performance. Besides, the autobiographical writings and the rare biographical sketches on Lācis do not present a coherent and complete account of her life that could possibly grant her a stable position in the cultural map of art and culture. Therefore, to a certain extent Lācis, as well as the researchers studying her oeuvre are complicit with her nonbelonging, resulting from her adventurous and striking life, as well as Lācis' failure to embrace the expected norms of femininity. An attempt to write down some fragments of herstory, to create a room of one's own for Asja Lācis, would connect the left wing intellectual endeavours of the 1920s in Latvia, Russia and Germany. By suggesting a different approach to our transcultural past through 'the dusty rags of our lives', it will find new ways to the future.